

A Study on Self Concept in Relation to Academic Achievement Among B.Ed Trainees

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research was to determine the relationship between the academic self-concept and academic performance. The sample consists of 100 B.Ed trainees from 6 colleges were chosen by using random sampling method. The data collection instrument for academic self-concept was a researcher made questionnaire. After verifying the scale's factorial structure, established levels of association between self-concept and academic performance, and predictive power of academic self-concept. The research finding showed a close relationship between academic self-concept and measures of academic performance. Academic self-concept powerfully and positive predicts general performance in literature and mathematics. Feel it is necessary to give adequate and sufficient attention to self-concept and self-esteem and teachers should be offered methodological guidance in order to work on these throughout the educational process.

INTRODUCTION

The self-concept is the information that we have about ourselves what we think we are like. Self-concept is persons perceptions of himself formed through experience and interpretations of the environment. Self-concept generally refers to the composite of ideas, feelings, and attitudes people have about themselves. Our self-perceptions vary from situation to situation and from one phase of our lives to another. These perceptions are influenced by a number of factors such as evaluations of significant others, reinforcements, and attributions of behavior. It further refers to the set of perceptions or reference points what the subject has about him: the set of characteristics, attributes, qualities and deficiencies,

capacities and limits, values and relationships that subject knows to be descriptive about its own and which he perceives as data concerning his identity.

The multifaceted and hierarchical model of self-concept suggested that general self-concept has four domains: the academic self-concept, social self-concept, emotional self-concept and physical self-concept. The academic self-concept can be divided further into second order specific subject self concepts like Urban, History, Mathematics, and Science etc. which can explain learner achievement in each subject. Social self-concept can be divided into peer self-concept and significant others self-concept. Emotional self concept refers to specific emotional states such as anxiety, love, happiness, depression, and anger. The physical self concept comprises physical ability and physical appearance self-concepts. The overall sense of self thus appears to be divided into at least three separate, but slightly related, self-concepts i.e. academics, emotional, and nonacademic.

Each one offers insights as to how teachers, can enhance their trainees self-concept. Researchers have been concerned with analyzing of relationships, both associative and predictive between self concept and academic performance. For example, observed that there is a persistent and significant relationship between the self-concept and academic achievement and that change in one seems to be associated with change in the other. Academic self-concept and academic achievement were strongly correlated. Findings of studies conducted on relationship between physical self-concept, social self-concept and

academic achievement were conflicting. There was no significant correlation between physical appearance and academic achievement and physical activity level was quite an independent entity that was not related to academic achievement. Sports and academic achievement appear to have a mutual influence on each other. There is a negative relationship between social self-concept and academic achievement. Academic self concept and academic achievement were best predictors of one another.

Despite the abundance of studies, however, no conclusive picture emerges about the extent of relationship between various self-concepts and academic achievement. It was intended to study the relationship between self-concept and academic achievement in order to rescue those trainees who may be victims of their own negative beliefs about themselves. The study is significant because the results may generate useful knowledge and understanding of the relationship between the female trainees self concept and academic achievement. The results of the study are likely to assist educators to improve trainees academic achievement and self-concept, if there appears to be some association between the two in country like Pakistan where success rate in education college exams, particularly in women colleges, is considerably low. The study results, therefore, are likely to be significant for trainees, teachers, parents and society at large in order to promote higher education among females. It is a general wish and aspiration of trainees, parents, educators and all stakeholders of education, that trainees and for that matter, learners at all levels of education, excel in their pursuance of academic work at all times. By self, we generally mean the conscious reflection of ones own being or identity, as an object separate from others or from the environment. There are a variety of ways to think about the self. Two of the most widely used terms are self-concept and self-esteem. Self-concept is the cognitive or thinking aspect of self (related to ones self-image) and generally refers to the totality of a complex, organized, and dynamic system of learned beliefs, attitudes and opinions that each person holds to be true about his or her personal existence. There is a great deal of research which shows that self-concept is, perhaps, the basis for all motivated behaviour. It is the self-concept that gives rise to possible selves, and it is possible selves that create the motivation for behavior. This supports the idea that ones paradigm or world view and ones relationship to that view provide the boundaries and circumstances within which we develop

our vision about possibilities. This is one of the major issues facing trainees and youth today.

Your self-concept is built upon perception upon how you perceive yourself based on the knowledge you have gained over a lifetime of experience. When it comes down to it, a self-concept is a Perception you have of your image, abilities, and in some ways a perception of your own individual uniqueness. This perception you have of your-self is based on the information you have gathered about your values, life roles, goals, skills, and abilities over time. Your self-concept is somewhat a collection of beliefs you have about your own nature, qualities, and behavior. Its about how you think and evaluate yourself at any given moment in time. But to truly understand what a self-concept is and its impact on your life, we first need to break down the three components of a self-concept.

The value of having a healthy self-concept becomes more evident when we recognize how much it influences our ability to manage our emotional experiences. However, it doesn't stop there. A healthy self-concept also determines how far you will step outside your comfort zone to solve a problem or achieve a goal. Moreover, it influences how you utilize your physiology while confronting challenges, obstacles, and problems. A healthy self-concept impacts the questions you typically ask yourself each day, and it affects how you interact with people, how you think about yourself, others, and circumstances. Putting all this together, your self-concept effectively determines what you will do or choose not to do at any given moment in time. It, therefore, influences your inherent potential to do, be, have and achieve your desired objectives.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

McInerney, D. M., Korpershoek, H., Wang, H., & Morin, A. J. (2018) known about the determinants of teachers psychological wellbeing, job satisfaction, occupational self-concept and quitting intentions. In this paper, teachers occupational attributes (i.e. professional and personal characteristics) were investigated as determinants. Henceforth, the Educator Motivation and Attribute Profile (EdMAP) scales were used to describe the nature of 1109 Hong Kong primary and secondary school teachers occupational attributes. Furthermore, the relationships with the teacher outcomes were investigated. Construct validity and reliabilities of the EdMAP scales were satisfactory. The results showed positive associations between teachers occupational attributes and their wellbeing, job satisfaction, and self

concept, and negative associations with quitting intentions.

Avramidis, E., Avgeri, G., & Strogilos, V. ((2018) addressed the social participation of integrated students with special educational needs (SEN) in upper primary regular classes in Greece alongside their perceptions of best friend quality. Social participation was defined as consisting of four key dimensions: students acceptance by classmates, friendships, social self-perceptions, and social interactions. Participants were 457 students with a mean age of 11.04 (SD = .83), of which 45 were diagnosed as having moderate learning difficulties. Fieldwork involved implementing a socio metric technique, conducting systematic observations and administering two psychometric instruments: the Self-Description Questionnaire (SDQ) and the Friendship Qualities Scale (FQS). In line with previous studies, students with SEN KumiYeboah, A., Dogbey, J., & Yuan, G. (2018) examined factors that promote/hinder the learning experiences and academic self- concept of minority students attending an online high school. Qualitative interviews were con- ducted with twenty-four African American, and sixteen Hispanic high B.Ed Trainees. The results showed that collaborative learning activities, access to resources, time convenience, student- teacher interactions, student-student interactions, improved academic behavior, and parental sup- port helped to enhance online learning experiences and academic self-concept of the minority students. On the contrary, the lack of social presence, and the lack of cultural inclusion in course content constrain online learning experiences and academic self concept of the students. The findings revealed some similarities between factors that influence minority students learning experiences online, and in face- to-face setting. The study also highlighted the need for teachers of online courses to under- stand the cultural backgrounds of minority students, and to use their knowledge to improve the learning experiences and academic self-concept of these students. Implications for teaching minority high B.Ed Trainees in an online environment, as well as suggestions for future research are provided. Gogol, K., Brunner, M., Mar- tin, R., Preckel, F., & Gtz, T. (2017). developed comprehensive model of affect and motivation is necessary for disentangling the variance of subject-specific measures into components that are (a) construct-specific and general- ize across different subjects, (b) subject-specific and common to different constructs, and (c) specific to a particular construct in a particular subject. In the present study, we developed and investigated an integrative model that

yields new insights concerning the generality and school- subject-specificity of affective-motivational constructs. To this end, we first examined structural models that could account for the hierarchical and subject-specific nature of academic self-concept, anxiety, and interest, respectively. In a second step, we combined these construct-specific models to investigate an integrative model that was able to simultaneously address between- and within-subject relations. We used data from four large-scale samples of ninth-graders (N = 8666146) on academic self-concept, interest, and anxiety in three subjects (mathematics, French, and German). Our results underscored the importance of the components at the more global level: The major part of reliable individual differences in subject-specific measures of affective- motivational constructs and their relations to achievement indicators (grades and standardized test scores) was explained by the general components of the affective-motivational constructs and the global affective-motivational appraisals of specific subjects rather than by the construct- and-subject-specific components. Overall, the structural architecture of the integrative model provides a way to simultaneously analyze complex within- and between-subject relations of affective-motivational constructs. Turner, H. A., Shattuck, A., Finkelhor, D., & Hamby, S. (2017) demonstrated the particularly damaging effects of exposure to multiple forms of victimization, or poly-victimization, on youth mental health. The primary objective of the present study is to begin to identify the mechanisms that help ex- plain its powerful impact. Analyses are based on two waves of longitudinal data from the National Survey of trainees Exposure to Violence (NatSCEV), conducted in 2008 and 2010, that comprised a telephone sample of 1,186 youth ages 10 to 17. Using structural equation modeling, we examine direct and indirect effects on distress symptoms of increased, decreased, and stable high poly-victimization between Waves 1 and 2 compared to no or low victimization in both waves. Specifically, we consider the extent to which reductions in core psychosocial resources, including family support, peer support, self-esteem, and mastery, mediate the relation- ship between these poly-victimization conditions and distress. Relative to stable low victimization, both increased poly-victimization and stable high poly-victimization were associated with de- clines in all four resources. However, only self- esteem and mastery significantly mediated the association between poly-victimization and distress, with mastery showing the strongest effect. Although significant indirect effects were evident, poly-victimization still had a strong direct effect on distress

with resource factors controlled. Findings support the hypothesis that the potent effect of poly-victimization on youth mental health is, in part, due to its damaging influence on core psychosocial resources.

Emmanuel, A. O., Adom, E. A., Josephine, B., & Solomon, F. K. (2014) investigated the relationship between achievement motivation, academic self concept and academic achievement of high B.Ed Trainees. In addition, the study found out the students profile to ascertain the levels of achievement motivation, self-concept, and their academic achievement. A total of 120 students selected from four high Colleges participated in the study. The results showed that, majority of the high B.Ed Trainees were highly motivated, have high self-concept and performed well on the Mathematics Achievement test. The study also found a significant correlation between self-concept and academic achievement. Again, there was a positive relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement but the correlation was not significant. The study confirms the importance of achievement motivation and academic self- concept to academic achievement and concluded by making insightful suggestions and recommendations to stakeholders in education in helping students to enhance their motivation and self-concept to improve on their academic performance. Preckel, F., Niepel, C., Schneider, M., & Brunner, M. (2013) Fostering social and academic self-concepts are central educational goals. During mid-adolescence academic engagement and success seem to be devalued by peers and to be negatively associated with students social standing. For this age group, is the development of a positive academic self-concept compatible with the development of a positive social self- concept?. Green, J., Liem, G. A. D., Martin, A. J., Colmar, S., Marsh, H. W., & McInerney, D. (2012) tested three theoretically/conceptually hypothesized longitudinal models of academic processes leading to academic performance. Based on a longitudinal sample of 1866 high- B.Ed Trainees across two consecutive years of high school (Time 1 and Time 2), the model with the most superior heuristic value demonstrated: (a) academic motivation and self-concept positively predicted attitudes toward school; (b) attitudes toward school positively predicted class participation and homework completion and negatively predicted absenteeism; and (c) class participation and homework completion positively predicted test performance whilst absenteeism negatively predicted test performance. Taken together, these findings provide support for the

relevance of the self-system model and, particularly, the importance of examining the dynamic relationships amongst engagement factors of the model. The study highlights implications for educational and psychological theory, measurement, and intervention. Marsh, H. W., & Martin, A. J. (2011). Academic self concept and academic achievement: Relations and causal ordering. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 81(1), 59-77. A positive self concept is valued as a desirable outcome in many disciplines of psychology as well as an important mediator to other outcomes. The present review examines support for the reciprocal effects model (REM) that posits academic self concept (ASC) and achievement are mutually reinforcing, each leading to gains in the other and its extension to other achievement domains and review the oretical, methodological, and empirical support for the REM. Critical features in this research are a theoretical emphasis on multidimensional perspectives that focus on specific components of self concept and a methodological focus on a construct validity approach to evaluating the REM.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To find out the level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees.
2. To find out the level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees with respect to gender.
3. To find out the level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees with respect to locality.
4. To find out the level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees with respect to medium of study.
5. To find out the level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees with respect to pedagogy
6. To study the a study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees.
7. To develop a questionnaire to assess the impact of self concept on achievement among B.Ed Trainees.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. Is there any significance mean score difference between gender and level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees?
2. Is there any significance mean score difference between locality related factors and level of study on

self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees?

3. Is there any significance mean score difference between medium of study related factors and level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees?
4. Is there any significance mean score difference between pedagogy and level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees?

HYPOTHESES

1. There will be a significant mean score difference between gender and level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees.
2. There will be a significant mean score difference between locality related factors and level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees.
3. There will be a significant mean score difference between medium of study related factors and level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees.
4. There will be a significant mean score difference between pedagogy and level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees.

VARIABLES

An independent variable is a variable that is expected to influence the dependent variables. Its value may be changed or altered, which is independent of any other variables. Also the following demographic variables were used as independent variables.

- Gender (Male/Female).
- Locality (Rural/Urban).
- Study Medium (Tamil/English).
- Pedagogy (Arts/Science/Language).

Dependent variable are those events which are by hypothesized as dependent on the changes in the dependent variable (Impact on academic achievement among B.Ed Trainees).

DESIGN OF THE STUDY

In the presence study normative survey method will be used. Survey research employee questioner and interview to our people who provide information about them selfs their attitude and believes demographic (Age, Gender, Income and So on) the survey method can be

classified into many, but according to the objectives and hypotheses in this presence study normative survey method will be adopted.

POPULATION AND SAMPLE

Coimbatore district is one of the districts in Tamilnadu, India. Coimbatore is finest education district of Tamilnadu. It is the second largest city in Tamilnadu and one of the fastest growing cities in Tamilnadu State. For the present study the investigator selects only 6 Education College in and around Coimbatore. Investigator selected Datas will be collected from the samples of 100 B.Ed Trainees of various Colleges.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

Sampling procedure is a definite plan determined before any data are actually collected for obtaining a sample from a given population under the simple random sampling technique. This sampling method is used for selecting samples. Simple random sampling is method in which each and every element in the population has an equal chance of getting selected. The study is based on primary data which is collected from 100 school students at higher secondary level and around Coimbatore district. The sample which was collected from various college located in and around Coimbatore is shown as below.

Table1.1 List of Colleges used for data collection

S. No	Name of the Colleges	Number of students
1.	Dr. Sns College of Education, Coimbatore	16
2.	Dr. N.G.P. College of Education, Coimbatore	14
3.	Century Foundation College of Education	17
4.	Hindusthan College of Education, Coimbatore	18
5.	Lisieux College of Education, Coimbatore	18
6.	Rkr College of Education, Coimbatore	17

TABLE 1.2

Distribution of samples based on variables

Category	Subgroups	Number	%	Total
Gender	Male	35	35	100
	Female	65	65	
Locality	Rural	63	63	100
	Urban	37	37	
Medium Study	Tamil	56	56	100
	English	44	44	
Pedagogy	Language	48	48	100
	Arts/ Science	52	52	

Figure 1: Relationship Between B.Ed Trainees Gender and level of study on self concept in B.Ed Trainees Academic Achievement

TESTING HYPOTHESIS 2:

There will be a significant mean score difference in level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees based on Locality(Rural/Urban).

TABLE 1.4 Mean Score difference and t-value of factors related to level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees based on Locality (Rural/Urban).

S. No.	Locality	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	Result
1	Rural	63	1.1752	99	-	S
2	Urban	37	1.3562			
Total		100	1.2657			

The Table 1.4 shows the mean score difference in level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees based on Locality (Rural/Urban).The calculate t value is statistically a significance at 0.05 levels and hence the hypotheses 2 is accepted. It can be concluded that there is a significant difference in mean score difference in level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed Trainees based on Locality.

Figure 2: Relationship Between B.Ed Trainees medium of instruction and level of study on self concept in B.Ed Trainees Academic Achievement

TESTING HYPOTHESIS 3:

There will be a significant mean score difference in level of self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees based on Education study medium (Tamil/English).

RESEARCH TOOL

Tool become another major consideration in an education research. The instrument employed for the collection of data required for the study of any problem is called tool. Tool employ distinction way of describing and qualifying the data the important tools of educational research include inter- view schedule, questionnaire, observation, rating scale, proficiency test, psychological tests and sociogram.

TESTING HYPOTHESIS 1:

There will be a significant mean score difference in level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees based on gender (Male/Female).

TABLE 1.3

Mean Score difference and f- value of factors related to level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees based on gender

S. No.	Gender	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	Result
1	Male	35	1.3856	99	2.051	S
2	Female	65	1.6129			
Total		100	1.4993			

The Table 1.3 shows the mean score difference in level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees based on gender (Male/Female).The calculate f value is statistically a significance at 0.05 levels and hence the hypotheses 1 is accepted. It can be concluded that there is a significant difference in mean score difference in level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees based on gender.

TABLE 1.5: Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees based on study medium. (Tamil/English).

S. No	Study medium	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	Result
1	Tamil	56	1.2832	99	0.872	NS
2	English	44	1.1732			
Total		100	1.1002			

The Table 1.5 shows the mean score difference in level of study among self concept in relation to academic achievement on B.Ed trainees based on Study Medium (Tamil/English). The calculate t value is statistically no significance at 0.05 levels and hence the hypotheses 3 is rejected. It can be concluded that there is no significant difference in mean score difference in level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement based on Study Medium (Tamil/English).

Figure 3: Relationship Between B.Ed Trainees school type and level of study level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees Academic Achievement

TESTING HYPOTHESIS 4:

There will be a significant mean score difference in level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees based on Pedagogy (Language/Arts/Science).

TABLE 1.6 : Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees based on Pedagogy (Language/Arts/Science).

S. No	Pedagogy	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	Result
1	Language	48	1.4121	99	-2.325	NS
2	Arts/ Science	52	1.0891			
Total		100	1.2506			

The Table 1.6 shows the mean score difference in level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees based on Pedagogy (Language/Arts/Science). The calculate t value is statistically a significance at 0.05 levels and hence the hypotheses 4 is accepted. It can be concluded that there is a significant difference in mean score difference in level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement based on Pedagogy (Language/Arts/Science).

Figure 4.3: Relationship Between B.Ed Trainees school location and level of study level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- There is a significant relationship between gender and level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees.
- There is a significant relationship between medium of instruction related factors and level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement.
- There is no significant relationship between pedagogy related factors and impact of self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees.
- There is a significant relationship between school location and level of study on self concept in relation to academic achievement among B.Ed trainees.

SUMMARY

- A study of self concept among B.Ed Trainees academic achievement was studied and the findings reveal that there is a significant difference with respect to gender, Locality and medium of study.
- A study of self concept among B.Ed Trainees academic achievement was studied and the findings reveal that there is no significant difference between level of study on higher secondary commerce students academic achievement with respect to Pedagogy.

LIMITATIONS

- The study has certain limitation, which are as follows:
- • Only 100 B.Ed are selected as sampling for the study.
- The project has been restricted to analyze and study of self concept academic achievement among B.Ed Trainees.
- The study is restricted to the B.Ed Trainees of Coimbatore.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS

- A Similar Study can be conducted for dissertation by taking more number of concepts and students.
- The study can be conducted to other Colleges around Tamilnadu.
- Present survey helps to investigate the impact level of self concept of B.Ed Trainees for academic achievement.
- A similar study can also be conducted using various variables.

The conclusion is that there is a significant relationship between gender, locality and pedagogy on impact of self concept among B.Ed Trainees. While taking decision on impact of self concept among B.Ed Trainees their pedagogy and locality has to be taken for decision making process.

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APPENDICES

PROFORMA FOR BASIC DATA

1. Name of the student :
2. Name of the Education College :
3. Gender : Male [] Female []
4. Locality : Rural [] Urban []
5. Study Medium : Tamil [] English []
6. Pedagogy : Language [] Arts/Science []

QUESTIONNAIRE

1	In your view,has self concept ever used for academic achievement?	Yes	No
2	Has self concept ever used for the learning of any of your family or friends?	Yes	No
3	Apart from self concept, are you aware different self learning activities?	Yes	No
4	Do you feel the way of learning is generally changing in recent years?	Yes	No
5	Have you heard of "Everyone is Unique"?	Yes	No
6	Do you think individual skills are something that is helping or is going to improve, Personally?	Yes	No
7	Do you think anything can be done to improve Self learning skills?	Yes	No
8	Have your ever taken, or do you regularly take, any steps for self improvement?	Yes	No
9	Is trainees already aware of self concept?	Yes	No
10	Is there anything self learning help us in Knowledge gaining?	Yes	No
11	Will learn through self learning be affect our personality?	Yes	No
12	Would a Self learning really change the academic achievement level of B.Ed Trainees?	Yes	No
13	Are self concept taught more than books?	Yes	No
14	Can self concept really essentials for B.Ed trainees in future?	Yes	No
15	Can self concept lead to better teaching?	Yes	No
16	Will self concept actually bring obstruction to some trainees?	Yes	No
17	Could self concept ever "Complex process"?	Yes	No
18	Have the Knowledge from self concept useful in exams?	Yes	No
19	Is there formal way of self concept is under way?	Yes	No
20	Are you concerned about self learning?	Yes	No
21	Are you aware of the impacts of self learning?	Yes	No
22	Are you aware of the causes and effects of self learning?	Yes	No
23	Do trainees also share their learning with others through self learning?	Yes	No
24	Couldn't the usage of technology cause the self learning?	Yes	No
25	Don't trainees learn more ideas from self learning than textbooks?	Yes	No
26	Hasn't education system improved or demoted after self learning adaptation?	Yes	No
27	Are there positive benefits from self learning?	Yes	No
28	Can we pay additional fee for self concept?	Yes	No
29	Are practical approaches are missed in self concept?	Yes	No
30	Will self concept cause the limited learning opportunities?	Yes	No